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Student retention and dropout in a PBL environment

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INTRODUCTION

Student retention is an issue that gathers increasing attention within the engineering education community. This is mainly due to the increasing need for engineers, paired with untenable dropout rates of 50%-60% in engineering programmes at many universities all over the world (1-3).

Until recently, Aalborg University (AAU) had avoided this development, even compared with other Danish universities (4). The common sense logic had been that Aalborg University adheres to a problem-based learning (PBL) approach, which inherently combats dropout. A very recent largescale English investigation about retention and dropout states that this is more than common sense logic:

'High-quality, student-centred learning and teaching is at the heart of improving the retention and success of all students. Academic programmes that have higher rates of retention and success make use of group-based learning and teaching, and varied learning opportunities, including real-world learning and work placements' (5).

Lately, however, we have started to see some AAU dropout rates at 30% and several research projects have been initiated to investigate this apparent paradox. As our initial studies also have shown, retention and dropout are phenomena with a complex causality of a practical, academic, pedagogical and social nature (4,6). A particular area of interest is, however, the extent to which our pedagogical PBL model has an impact on these new trends and whether it should be modified. As an important step in this area, this paper evaluates existing literature to research state-of-the-art methods of addressing retention, dropout and PBL learning environments.

1. RESEARCH DESIGN

1.1. Research question

This paper aims to investigate the phenomena of student retention and dropout in a problem-based learning (PBL) environment by means of a literature review. Because most dropout takes place within the first year of college (5), we will limit our focus to first-year students. Consequently, the research question guiding the literature review is as follows:

What are the dynamics at play between a problem-based learning environment in engineering education on the one hand and first-year student retention and dropout on the other?

After defining the core concepts employed in this paper, we will go through the methodology behind the literature review, after which we will present the results of the review and discuss the implications for further research within the area of retention/dropout and PBL.

1.2. Theoretical core concepts defined

In this section, we define our two main concepts and the relationship between them. We also define a few related concepts, because either we use them in our search string and the analyses, or they were important in some of the studies we analysed.

Following Kolmos (7) a problem-based learning environment refers to an innovative learning approach on a curriculum level that combines specific cognitive, collaborative and content-related strategies. Cognitively the learning is both problem- and project-based and situated in a specific context. Collaboratively the learning takes place in participant-directed teams. In terms of content, the learning is interdisciplinary, exemplary and emphasises theory as well as practice, including research methodologies. It aims to model real-world situations and guide the learners to develop interdisciplinary, deep-content learning within an exemplary discipline area, as well as foster problem-solving and collaborative skills. As such, it is a huge leap away from traditional college teaching and puts new qualitative and quantitative learning demands on both students and faculty. PBL activities or approaches can also be a pedagogical learning strategy employed at a workshop or course, in which case it normally refers to problem- or team-based activities. Active learning activities or approaches are learning strategies that in this context refer more generally to 'any activity in which every student must think, create or solve a problem (3). It can also be applied on any level – workshop, course or curriculum – and does not necessarily entail problem- or team-based activities.

Retention is defined as the likelihood of a student remaining in university (8) and can be attributed to a number of factors beyond their academic ability when they enter their first year. *Dropout* is defined as the likelihood of a student leaving university (ibid). Two other important concepts appearing in the literature review are *engagement* and *persistence* (9). *Engagement* is defined as the time and effort students devote to a learning a task. *Effort* here is understood as affective, cognitive and metacognitive

mobilisation. *Persistence*, on the other hand, is the conscious choice one makes to carry on with an activity despite the obstacles or difficulties one may encounter. Even if engagement and persistence do not equal retention and dropout, the two pairs are strongly correlated. *Dynamics at play* is the relationship between the two main concepts. Below we analyse the kinds of relationships that the literature generally imagines between retention and dropout on one hand, and a problem-based learning environment on the other.

1.3. Methodology

To carry out the literature search we first concentrated on the search string's specific words. We aimed to find literature within the engineering education field concerning retention and dropout for first-year students. Each area of interest was scrutinised for relevant synonyms. Two people participated in this endeavour, including one librarian. We came up with the following words for each search:

- Engineer – STEM – sciences – natural sciences
- PBL – problem based – problem-based – project based – project-based – student-centered – active learning
- Drop out – dropout – attrition – retention – retain – holding power – withdraw – persistence
- Student – freshman – freshmen – undergrad – bachelor

The search string ended up looking like this: (engineer* OR STEM OR sciences OR 'natural science') AND (student* OR freshman OR freshmen OR undergrad* OR bachelor*) AND (PBL OR 'problem based' OR 'problem-based' OR 'project based' OR 'project-based' OR 'student-centered' OR 'active learning') AND ('drop out' OR dropout* OR attrition OR retention OR retain OR 'holding power' OR withdraw* OR persistence). Thus, we wanted literature that combined the four areas of interest. We carried out the search in four databases central to education: Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC), PsycARTICLES / PsycINFO, Academic Search Premier and Web of Science. We looked only for peer-reviewed articles and there were no restrictions concerning the date of the papers. However, we did restrict the search to include only papers that had the search words in the title or the abstract. We carried out the search in November 2016. When we retrieved the data, every abstract was read through twice. The first reading was done to get an initial understanding of the literature at hand and determine what kinds of categories were operational. After the second reading, the researchers determined whether each paper had been placed in the proper category. Finally, we scrutinised papers of particular interest and analysed them in relation to the research question.

2. FINDINGS

2.1. Articles retrieved

An overview of the article output is shown in Table 1. In total, 87 papers were retrieved in the search, the oldest from 2000. Most of them we found via ERIC. Leaving out repeating papers, Academic Search Premier yielded another 30; PsycARTICLES / PsycINFO yielded three and Web of Science provided a single paper. Most of the 87 articles – 48 articles to be specific – did not cover the subject of student retention and dropout. They dealt with the quality and retention of the knowledge that students would

acquire from different learning strategies. At most, they mentioned student retention and dropout in a sentence or two. Consequently, we left them out. Twenty articles covered issues not related to student retention in college. Issues like student retention and dropout in high school, how teachers and management related to the issue of retention or how student retention would look in a non-engineering discipline.

Another seven articles dealt with the theme of retention and dropout during the first year of college within engineering education. However, they dealt with the subject on a course level, rather than a programme level. The authors usually had an exclusive focus on a specific course (e.g. a math course), trying to determine whether active learning or problem-based learning would make the specific course more forthcoming and digestible for the students so that they would not fail the course. Only 12 articles addressed student retention on an overall programme level, while at the same time considering the merits of active learning in general (6 studies) or PBL (6 studies). Out of these 12 articles, we could not find a full paper for one active learning programme, and had to dismiss it. Nine articles were positive toward active learning/PBL learning strategies. Active learning and PBL learning strategies were seen strictly as part of the solution for retention and dropout issues. Only two articles, both by the same Canadian main author, investigated how PBL curricula might also increase persistence and lower engagement of engineering students during the first year of college. In the following section we will go through the 11 articles on a programme level more thoroughly.

Table 1. Overview of articles retrieved in the literature search

	Eric	'Academic'	'PsycINFO'	Web of Science	Total no. articles by category
Knowledge Quality/ Retention Active L strategy	15	11			26
Knowledge Quality/ Retention PBL strategy	14	8			22
Retention Act L Strategy Course Level	3				3
Retention PBL strategy Course level	3	1			4
Retention Active L strategy Programme Level	5	1			6
Retention PBL strategy Programme level	3	2		1	6
Other	10	7	3		20
Total no. articles	53	30	3	1	87 in total

2.2. An active learning strategy in service of retention

Retention was the focal point for this category of papers. It dealt with the question of what active learning strategies can do for retention on a programme level, while also looking at other, more general, retention factors like financial issues. All five papers stemmed from American contexts and all of them celebrated active learning strategies as a tool to secure retention. The specific arguments and the weighing of them differed, though, as did their definitions of active learning. Table 2 gives an overview of the different types of active learning employed and the context of retention. Four papers (1,2,10,11) reported results of a changed curriculum in which active learning played a larger role. One paper (3) went through a conceptual model for improving persistence of college students in STEM based on a literature review. Even if all papers acknowledged that the character of the single student played a role in retention, they all shared a conviction that institutional characteristics and initiatives are important. Xu (1) underlined that STEM areas are inherently challenging, demanding an institutional focus on a good learning environment such as smaller class sizes and in-class interaction with instructors.

Table 2 Overview of active learning activities, the relationship between active learning and retention and core beliefs about retention in general for each study

	Type of Active Learning	Relation between Active Learning and Retention	Understanding of Retention in general
(1)	Interesting learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student-centred teaching practice • Authentic research activities 	Active Learning → Retention by default	Challenging nature of STEM demands good learning environment
(2)	Engineering learning communities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort courses • Activating L technics • Peer study groups • Mentor/Tutor 	Active learning → Sense of community → Retention	Chilliness of climate, financial issues and poor math skills are core challenges
(10)	Team-based learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative groups • 'Flipped classroom' with application 	Active learning → Active and accountable science students → Retention	Collaborative instructional strategies lead to retention and other learning outcomes
(3)	Any activity in which a student must think, create or solve	Active learning → Identification as scientists, better understanding → Retention	Early research experience, Active Learning and learning communities provide persistence
(11)	Student learning communities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort courses • Activating L technics • Peer study groups • Mentor/Tutor 	Active learning → Sense of belonging, self-confidence and improved learning → Retention	Collaborative structures provide academic and social support

Articles (10) and (3) took the academic focus a little further, insisting that a scientific identity is a basic requirement for retention, underlining the need for methods like early research experiences and active-learning strategies resembling what a scientist does. Articles (2) and (11) emphasised sense of community and belonging as important factors in retention, urging experimentation with different kinds of student learning communities.

2.3. A PBL learning strategy in service of retention

In the four papers about retention and problem-based learning strategies, retention was a major concern for which varying degrees of PBL strategies provided an excellent solution. Two stemmed from American contexts, one from Canada and one from South Africa. (12) looked at the employability of a PBL strategy on a course level, whereas the others looked at some initiatives that involved broader parts of the curriculum. For these three studies (13-15) PBL learning environments were also interesting because they yielded other positive results, such as improvements in the students' communicative, critical and professional skills. No findings pointed in the direction of PBL learning environments having negative impacts on retention. In general, little was said about potential challenges of PBL learning environments – this was limited to challenges and costs of implementation or group dynamics.

Table 3 Type of PBL, relationship between PBL and retention and understanding of retention in general for each study

	Type of PBL	Relation between PBL and Retention	Understanding of Retention in general
(12)	Change Chem initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small design projects as part of courses • Authentic prob. descriptions • Teamwork 	Promising relation: Increased learning and identity with engineering Some dysfunctional team issues	Building engineering identity, sup. social interdependence and achievement will attract women and minorities, fit workforce demands and secure retention
(13)	GDW initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary project module • Real world game design 	PBL → Increased motivation, disciplinary and communicative skills, increased quality, group dynamics and retention	Retention is one issue that can be addressed by the introduction of PBL
(14)	Integrated PBL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem-based curriculum • Collaborative teaching strategies 	PBL → Collaborative, critical and prof. skills building, earlier maturity, self-directedness and retention	Curricula changes, faculty education and introduction of PBL is the solution to retention issues
(15)	PBL ala Maastricht <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated • Problem-based • Seven jump 	PBL → Impact the learning style of at-risk students and thus improve retention	At-risk students in South Africa do benefit from a PBL strategy in terms of retention

2.4. A PBL learning environment in terms of engagement and persistence

Only two papers intimately dealt with challenges of a PBL learning environment that may have potentially affected retention and dropout. The papers were written by the same team of researchers who were associated with the Centre for Research in Higher Education at the Université de Sherbrooke in Canada. Université de Sherbrooke is a university that has had PBL learning environments within medicine since the late 1980s, and in their engineering education since around 2000.

(9) and (16) presented a predictive conceptual model of the factors that influenced the engagement and persistence of students within an innovative PBL curriculum, similar to the Aalborg model. The papers also presented the results of a questionnaire study and an interview study, carried out in medicine and two engineering programmes, to gain insight and test the model.

According to Bedard et al. (9,16), the engagement and persistence of a student in a PBL learning environment can be predicted based on four factors: the student's *self-efficacy*, *stress level*, *level of competence in new cognitive tools* and their *theories and beliefs about knowledge*. Following Bandura, Bedard et al. (9) defined self-efficacy as the notion that the more one thinks they are effective, the more they will persist. Stress was defined as the particular relationship between individuals and their environment, when the latter exceeds the resources available to the individual. New cognitive tools – demanded by a new learning environment – included knowledge articulation and reflexive thinking. The student's theories and beliefs about knowledge were important in a curriculum that introduces 'contextualisation of knowledge' as one of its main characteristics. Reaching the level of relativism (contextual lenses) as opposed to subjectivism (personal truth) and dualism (right or wrong) will make a difference for the student's engagement and persistence.

What is interesting about this research is that the best predictor of a student's engagement and persistence was the support that reduced stress. If a student found this support high, the engagement and persistence of that same student was equally high. In fact, the stress factor was singled out as the factor that explained most of the variance found in the research, especially related to engagement. Self-efficacy, which is usually singled out as important, played a minor role. An overview of the arguments and suggested activities are given in Table 4.

As can be seen from Table 4, initiatives that helped the students overcome the stress of a new, demanding learning environment positively affected engagement and persistence. Stress levels were higher in the first year due to the new learning environment and the lack of appropriate learning strategies. Bedard et al. (16) emphasised that different types of curriculum resulted in different factors carrying the most weight. For example, computer science did not see stress-related issues at the top as other programmes did. Instead, one of the new cognitive tools, knowledge attrition, carried the most weight. Bedard et al. pointed to the fact that within computer science, it is vital to understand and articulate abstract mathematical knowledge, and the tutors placed great emphasis on this, which could both be reasons for this specific outcome.

Table 4 Relationship between PBL and engagement/persistence and activities that affect engagement and persistence positively in a PBL learning environment

	Type of PBL	Relation between PBL and engagement and persistence	Activities that affect engagement and persistence positively
(9) and (16)	Innovative PBL curriculum	<p>Engagement and persistence in PBL curriculum can be predicted based on four factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-efficacy • Stress • New cognitive tools • Theories and beliefs about knowledge <p>The support measures that reduce stress is the better predictor of engagement and persistence</p> <p>Collaborative work is effective in reducing stress, however conflicts are stressful</p> <p>Disciplinary fields influence which factors carry the day</p>	<p>Knowledge production in a real life problem context</p> <p>Enough time to project work</p> <p>Support from peers, faculty and mentors</p> <p>Stable learning environments with tutors</p> <p>Scaffolding measures for managing time and organising learning practices</p> <p>Clear objectives and expectations of the curriculum</p> <p>Collaborative spirit rather than competition</p> <p>Evaluation process coherent with PBL learning mode</p>

3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

The literature review shows that very few studies overall have dealt with the dynamics at play between PBL learning environments within engineering education and college student retention and dropout rates. This is the most basic and telling finding – not a lot is known within this area.

Of the studies that dealt with the issue, the majority experienced the dynamics at play to be purely positive. PBL and active learning were seen as part of a solution to a problem that is increasingly present in the world of engineering education. There seems to be very little inquiry into the question of whether a PBL learning environment could be anything but positive in terms of retention and dropout. Active learning and PBL strategies enhance scientific identity, improve learning quality and resemble what scientists and workplaces do. They provide peer support and nourish a sense of community and belonging, factors that support retention and diminish dropout, as we also saw with the introductory quotation. This is vital in a STEM context, where the disciplines seem to be inherently challenging and the demand for workforce is rising.

How can we then explain the contradictory situation at AAU? Why have retention rates changed?

What the Canadian findings seem to teach us is that while innovative curricula, like PBL, improves retention for the reasons stated above, and in particular by reducing students' stress, too much of a new thing might also trigger stress. PBL often necessitates that students develop more autonomy, responsibility and new learning strategies, as well as self-awareness about the value of these student-centred

activities. This has been the case at AAU for a long time, though. What the Canadian study also shows is that some factors positively enhance engagement and persistence. Among these include: enough time for project work; support from peers, faculty, and mentors; clear objectives and expectations of the curriculum; a collaborative spirit rather than a competitive one and an evaluation process coherent with the PBL learning mode.

Some of the inquiries that we have already used (4,6) with students at AAU suggest that they feel more stressed in general. Among other things, they lack enough time to do their project work and believe course activities take up a lot of energy. Speculatively, there has seemingly been a general increase in course activity at AAU, an increased competitive spirit and the evaluation process has definitely been under heavy pressure to become much more individualised. It is, however, outside this paper's scope to speculate further regarding the underlying reasons. Regardless of what makes the AAU students more stressed, this literature review advises us to strike a balance, where overcoming the stress of a new learning environment is possible, while at the same time harvesting the many benefits of PBL learning environments.

The research into these areas is far from sufficient and more research will be necessary. Based on this literature review, in an AAU context, issues that stand out include: new ICT-driven generations of students entering university. To what extent do these new generations of students alter the fit of the existing pedagogical PBL model? Economic pressure and pressure from faculty toward more traditional knowledge training imply a more diluted PBL learning environment. Do we then ultimately put students in a clamp by asking them to honour both traditional and innovative learning pedagogies – adding to a stressful environment? These and other questions will be addressed in our research projects concerning retention and dropout in the coming years within the area of engineering education.

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